

Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science in Computer Engineering

Performance Enhancement of Convolution Neural Network for COVID-19 Classification

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Abstract

Understanding and classifying Chest X-Ray images are of great significance for COVID-19 diagnosis. An essential first step in the fight against COVID-19 is a positive chest X-ray for infected patients. Research has suggested leveraging publicly accessible datasets of chest X-rays to automatically diagnose COVID-19 using AI algorithms based on deep learning. Nonetheless, radiographic CXRs are still hard to come by. This may reduce the effectiveness of methods based on deep learning for COVID-19 detection. Similar to convolution neural networks, deep learning networks require a large volume of training data. The best set of hyperparameters among the possible combination provide an appropriate way to learn deep representations without widespread use of labeled training data. Each generated X-ray belongs to one of the two classes COVID-19 positive or normal. The optimization process aimed to optimize four hyperparameters: 1) data size, 2) batch size, 3) learning rate, 4) dropout with base convolution neural networks model VGG16. Extensive experiments are performed by considering the proposed and the competitive machine learning techniques on the chest X-Ray image. The results is compared to other available model to observe the efficient methods. Extensive analysis shows that the proposed model can classify the chest X-Ray image at a good accuracy rate when model is fit with optimal hyperparameters.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Convolution neural networks, Hyperparameters, Data augmentation, Covid-19 classification, Chest X-ray, Fine tuning

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAD	Computer-aided diagnosis
CNN	Convolution Neural Network
CXR	Chest X-ray
GAN	Generative Adversarial Network
RT-PCR	Reverse Transcription-Polymerase Chain Reaction
VGG	Visual Geometry Group

CHAPTER 1

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the primary technologies for classification and prediction, artificial intelligence (AI), has been researched and used in a number of industries. In the medical field, image data classification has been applied extensively. Techniques for computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) have proven beneficial in a number of ways. Early illness diagnosis and classification in humans have been made easier by CAD approaches [1] .

1.1 Background

People who are afflicted by the global pandemic caused by the novel virus, SARS-CoV-2, have respiratory illnesses. In the serological test, a blood sample from a person who may be infected is examined for the presence of particular anti-bodies. The scarcity of these screening methods is one of their main disadvantages. The difficult manual procedure of performing these tests, for which many poor nations lack the necessary knowledge, is another disadvantage [2]. An alternative screening technique, Reverse transcription–polymerase chain reaction (real time RT–PCR), one of the most accurate laboratory methods for detecting Covid-19. In a similar fashion chest X-rays (CXRs) have been widely used to detect COVID-19-positive cases [3].

Data augmentation refers to a group of methods that increase the quantity and caliber of training datasets so that Deep Learning models can be constructed with greater accuracy. Data Augmentation can improve the performance of models and expand limited datasets to take advantage of the capabilities of big data [4].

CNN models used in classifying COVID-19 CXR images and also in the field of medical imaging. Optimal hyperparameter selection of CNN is one of the challenges for CNNs [2] to be reliable with limited quantity and variety of samples. The use of data augmentation techniques to produce variation in samples for COVID-19 has already been reported in the literature [5] affected. Hyperparameter knobs can be tuned to control the behavior of CNN leaving big impact on model training [6] . Proposed intend to enhance CNN model by varying CNN hyperparameter and fine tuning that improves Covid-19 detection and classification.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The use of CNN is very popular for image classification. Many dynamic CNN models have been used over the years to diagnose diseases. Many researchers implemented and provided the accuracy and efficiency of the CNN model in image classification. The recent pandemic of the Corona virus around the world has created the necessity of an AI model to separate the COVID-19 positive and negative cases with the help of quick screening of chest X-ray images. The performance of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in classifying COVID-19 cases from medical imaging data can be significantly affected by the choice of hyperparameters such as batch size, learning rate, dropout rate, and data size. But it poses a challenge to determine the optimal values for these hyperparameters due to their interdependencies and computational constraints. Hyperparameter tuning of COVID-19-detecting CNN models is a relatively under-researched area. A recent study done in the COVID-19 classification of positive and normal cases of chest X-rays with CNNs suggested that tuning with these hyperparameters leads to better generalization [6]. Therefore, experiments with different numbers of available data sizes and hyperparameter tuning methods must be put into practice to improve CNN models.

1.3 Research objectives

The main objectives is: To enhance performance of CNN for Covid-19 CXR image classification.

1.4 Significance/Rationale of the study

Many machine learning models and algorithms are used for Covid-19 classification and detection. Numbers of research may be based on different type of imaging techniques such as X-rays and CT scans. The studies are focused to find a method which is reliable in classification and detection of Covid-19 infection given a medical image of chest X-rays. Use training methodology, with CNNs hyperparameter tuning is the key idea that generalize the model enough to perform well.

CHAPTER 2

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are various research and studies done in this field. The contextual and relevant research works related to this study are reviewed as follows:

Maram Mahmoud A. Monshi, Josiah Poon, Vera Chung, and Fahad Mahmoud A. Monshi [6] Suggested Tuning of hyperparameter combined with other regularization techniques, it produces better generalization to unseen data. In future, intend to tune more hyperparameters other than learning rate.

Waheed, M. Goyal, D. Gupta, A. Khanna, F. Al-Turjman, and P. R. Pinheirov [7], proposed an ACGAN based model that generates synthetic CXR image to enlarge the dataset and to improve the performance of CNN. The result shows the synthesized image of CXR have significant visualizations and features that help in the detection of Covid-19.

K. Das, S. Kalam, C. Kumar, and D. Sinha [8], Proposed VGG-16 is the best suite for the detection and classification of Covid-19 positive cases from the chest X-ray images. The performance evaluation of the proposed model proves that it outperforms two similar types of existing automated Covid-19 screening models. It helps in reducing the workload of radiologists and accelerates the screening process to identify Covid-19 positive patients.

T. Karras, T. Aila, S. Laine, and J. Lehtinen [9], explained a new training methodology for generative adversarial networks. The key idea is to grow both the generator and discriminator progressively as Progressive Growing GANs. While the quality of our results is generally high compared to earlier work on GANs, and the training is stable in large resolutions.

A. P. Adedigba, S. A. Adeshina, O. E. Aina, and A. M. Aibinu,[2], Suggested optimizing CNN hyperparameters result in outstanding effects on the extraction of features from CXR related to the diagnosis of COVID-19. Tuning of hyperparameter combined with other regularization techniques such as data augmentation, it produces better generalization to unseen data

In the study by Podder et al [10] who proposed a new deep learning (DL) framework-optimized DenseNet201 for lung diseases (LDDNet) for the analysis of lung diseases, including COVID-19 and pneumonia, from both chest CT scans and X-ray (CXR) images. For a given set of parameters, the performance results of LDDNet were better than the ResNet152V2 and XceptionNet.

DenseNet201 model performed well in the study by Rahman et al. [11] who also used transfer learning approach. For this, they applied four pre-trained models, AlexNet, ResNet18, DenseNet201, and SqueezeNet. The highest classification accuracy of normal and covid images were 98%, 95%, and 93.3%, respectively obtained using ResNet18 model.

In the review by Kora et al. [12], the authors investigated Transfer Learning (TL) architectures for automated medical image analysis. Their review showed that ResNet, VGGNet, and Inception are the most widely used.

These studies demonstrated the differences in performance and accuracy between different COVID-19 CXR detection models and architectures. Each method has pros and cons, with some models outperforming others in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, FAR, and AUC.

In summary, deep learning-based approaches, particularly a transfer learning methodology, have demonstrated significant potential for automated COVID-19 detection on chest radiographs. Predefined and fixed CNNs model can be enhanced by hyperparameter selection and tuning as found in Maram Mahmoud A. Monshi, Josiah Poon, Vera Chung, and Fahad Mahmoud A. Monshi [6] research paper to make reliable Covid-19 detection and classification. However, a thorough evaluation of several models for this task is required to find the most effective model with appropriate hyperparameter and guide additional studies in this field.

CHAPTER 3

3. METHODOLOGY

This research firstly describes the used datasets and their characteristics. Then explain the CNN architecture for the CXR images classification task along with CNNs Hyperparameters which will be used in performance enhancement to improved Covid-19 detection and classification. The primary challenge is the use of default parameterized CNN. The solution is tuning of appropriate hyperparameter for specific domain. In other hand limited amount of data availability for training the CNN is another problem. Use of generative adversarial network (GAN) is one of the option to increase the dataset but among its many drawbacks are mode collapse, spatial deformities, inadvertent modifications, and the production of high-frequency sounds [13]. So using at most real datasets rather than generative fake image will provide business value and make model stable.

The proposed framework is shown in the figure 3-1, which is divided into two sub-section. X-ray image dataset from the kaggle is used to train the VGG16 [14] and other pre-trained CNN state-of-art-models [15] by changing some parameters and data size variation with 224 * 224 image.

Figure 3-1: Model framework

3.1 Data Source and Preprocessing

There are many sets of data available on internet of chest X-ray that to be used for Covid-19 classification but finding the right dataset is crucial. So among available datasets “Kaggle Dataset” [16] is used.

This dataset contain two class of chest x-ray

- i) Covid-19 positive CXR
- ii) Normal CXR

Figure 3-2: Data distribution sample (Data size: 15000)

Performance analysis of VGG16 is performed with variation of data size along with regularization techniques for improved COVID-19 detection. Regularization, which involve the use of optimal hyper-parameters especially input data size and batch size pipeline with learning rate and dropout.[17] Since, VGG16 is used as base model and transfer learning is performed, these parameter tuning is done. Epochs of classification models are set to be 15. Image size of 224 * 224 and the training, testing and validation ratio of the dataset is set to be 70%, 15% and 15% respectively and Google Colaboratory is used for computation and performance evaluation CASE tool.

Figure 3-3: High-Resolution sample images from the original data set

3.2 CNN Architecture

VGG16 is a convolution neural net (CNN) architecture which was used to win ILSVR (Image net) competition in 2014. It is considered to be one of the excellent vision model architecture till date [15]. Proposed method is based on the well-established pre-trained DL model (VGG-16).

As its name implies, VGG16 is a deep neural network with 16 layers. That makes VGG16 a rather large network with 138 million parameters in total. [18]. ConvNets, a type of artificial neural network, are sometimes referred to as convolutional neural networks. An input layer, an output layer, and several hidden layers make up a convolutional neural network. Convolutional neural networks, or CNNs, like the VGG16 model are thought to be among the best computer vision models available today. [19].

Figure 3-4: Architecture of VGG16 [18]

Figure 3-5: Layers in VGG16 [19]

3.2.1 Input Layer

An image of size 224 by 224 is sent into VGGNet. The model's developers cropped a 224×224 portion from each image's center in order to maintain a constant image input size for the ImageNet competition.[18] The image from the kaggle dataset are of different resolution and resized to 224×224 for training and extracting the feature images.

3.2.2 Convolution Layer

The convolutional filters of VGG use the smallest possible receptive field of 3×3. VGG also uses a 1×1 convolution filter as the input's linear transformation.

3.2.3 ReLU Activation

The main innovation of AlexNet for cutting training time is the Rectified Linear Unit Activation Function (ReLU) component. ReLU is a linear function that yields zero for negative inputs and a matching output for positive inputs. To maintain the spatial resolution following convolution, VGG uses a fixed convolution stride of 1 pixel (the stride value shows how many pixels the filter “moves” to cover the complete space of the picture).

3.2.4 Pooling Layer

The number of parameters and dimensionality of the feature maps produced by each convolution phase are decreased by adding a pooling layer after a series of convolutional layers. Given the quick increase in the number of filters accessible from 64 to 128 to 256 and finally 512 in the final layers, pooling is essential.

3.2.5 Fully Connected Layer (FC)

In this FC layer, each neuron of all layers is connected with the neurons of the previous layer. This layer helps to produce and then forward the output from the extracted features to the output layers.

Figure 3-6: CNN with fully connected layer and sigmoid as the output layer

3.2.6 Output Layer

The output layer includes a label that is encoded as a single-hot label. In this study, the output layer provides the importance of the outcome of Normal or COVID.

3.2.7 Activation Function

A neuron's output can be limited to a predetermined range by using its activation function. Another name for it is Transfer Function. An activation function's fundamental characteristics are its nonlinearity, differentiability, and boundedness.

3.2.7.1 Sigmoid Activation

The last layer in the CNN layer is the sigmoid. Sigmoid activation function exists between 0 and 1. The sigmoid function is used for the two-class logistic regression.

$$\text{Sigmoid}(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

3.3 Hyperparameters Tuning

Complex machine learning algorithms are now possible to construct thanks to high processing power and easy access to massive amounts of data. The quantity of data needed to train a model rises in tandem with its complexity.

Data is not the only factor in the performance of a model. Complex models have many hyperparameters that need to be correctly adjusted or tuned in order to make the most out of them and here aimed to optimize four hyperparameters: 1) data size, 2) batch size, 3) learning rate 4) dropout

Learning rate controls how much to change the model in response to the estimated error each time the model weights are updated. Batch size is one of the most important hyperparameters to tune in modern deep learning systems. The batch size is a hyperparameter that defines the number of samples to work through before updating the internal model parameters. One hyperparameter that specifies how many times the learning algorithm will run through the training dataset is the number of epochs. Using too few or too many epochs can cause the network to underfit or overfit. So optimal selection of batch size make model robust. Another parameter is regularization of drop out. Dropout is a powerful regularization technique that can significantly reduce overfitting. By randomly dropping out neurons during training, dropout encourages the network to learn more robust representations of the input data.

3.4 Tools and Experimental Setup

The Google Colaboratory platform was used for the experiment's training, testing, and validation phases. Notebooks and manual setup are not required. With its support for numerous well-known machine learning libraries, including the Python environment, which operates in the cloud and allows users to run code, it can train sophisticated machine learning models more quickly than other general-purpose computers by utilizing powerful computational resources.

General programming language Python 3.9 is used to implement the project. TensorFlow, an open source platform for machine learning related projects, is used to implement convolutional neural network. The numpy and pandas, python libraries is used for data structure and data analysis along with Matplotlib to plot the graphs. Data are arranged in different folder for different experiments and mounted to colaboratory via Google drive.

CHAPTER 4

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Binary data classification are labeled as 0 and 1. In this research target class is COVID-19 CXR images which is labeled as 0 and non-target class which is Normal CXR image is labeled as 1.

True Positive (TP): Correctly classified as COVID-19 (0)

True Negative (TN): Correctly classified as Normal (1)

False Positive (FP): Incorrectly classified as COVID-19 (0) when they are actually Normal (1)

False Negative (FN): Incorrectly classified as Normal (1) when they are actually COVID -19 (0)

Then, evaluation metrics are:

$$\text{Specificity (TNR)} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \dots\dots\dots \text{(ii)}$$

$$\text{False Alarm Rate (FAR)} = \frac{FP}{FP+TN} \dots\dots\dots \text{(iii)}$$

$$\text{Sensitivity (Recall)} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \dots\dots\dots \text{(iv)}$$

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \dots\dots\dots \text{(v)}$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \dots\dots\dots \text{(vi)}$$

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \dots\dots\dots \text{(vii)}$$

4.1 Evaluation of experiment-1

Table 4.1-1: Data segmentation for experiment-1

Train Normal Image	1750	Train COVID Image	1750
Test Normal Image	375	Test COVID Image	375
Val Normal Image	375	Val COVID Image	375

In this section, total image **5000** is used. Split ratio of 70:15:15 is shown in the Table 4.1-1. Experiments is performed with different batch size with fixed epoch 15. Image are distributed with balanced condition. Each classes consist 2500 CXR data as shown in figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1: Data distribution for experiment-1

4.1.1 Performance metrics of Batch 16

Table 4.1-2: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment one with batch size 16

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.797
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.077
Precision	0.888
Specificity	0.922
Accuracy	0.868
F1-Score	0.840

4.1.1.1 Visualization of Batch 16

Figure 4-2: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-3: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-1 batch 16

The model correctly identified 325 COVID-19 images as positive and missed 50 COVID-19 cases, incorrectly classifying them as normal. The model made a mistake of classifying 49 normal images as COVID-19 cases when they were not whereas model correctly identified 326 normal images as negative.

4.1.2 Performance metrics of Batch 32

Table 4.1-3: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment one with batch size 32

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.816
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.070
Precision	0.900
Specificity	0.930
Accuracy	0.880
F1-Score	0.856

In this case, model correctly identified approximately 81.6% of COVID CXR images. Precision measures the proportion of true positive predictions out of all positive predictions made by model. In this case, model predicts a COVID CXR, its correct approximately 90% of the time. It provides a balanced measure of both precision and recall.

4.1.2.1 Visualization of Batch 32

Figure 4-4: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-5: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-1 batch 32

True Positives (TP) represent the number of correctly classified COVID-19 images, which is 339 in this case. False Negatives (FN) denote the instances where COVID-19 images were incorrectly classified as Normal, and there are 36 such cases. False Positives (FP) indicate the number of Normal images incorrectly classified as COVID-

19, with a count of 28. Lastly, True Negatives (TN) represent the number of correctly classified Normal images, totaling 347. An ROC curve helps you visualize how well model distinguishes between positive and negative cases. In this case, the AUC (Area under the Curve) is 0.87, which indicates that your model's ability to discriminate between COVID and Normal CXR images is quite good.

4.1.3 Performance metrics of Batch 64

Table 4.1-4 : Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment one with batch size 64

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.777
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.068
Precision	0.899
Specificity	0.932
Accuracy	0.865
F1-Score	0.833

4.1.3.1 Visualization of Batch 64

Figure 4-6: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-7: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-1 batch 64

The number of COVID-19 CXR images that were correctly classified as COVID-19 are 333. In other hand, incorrectly classified as normal (false negatives) are 42. Normal CXR images that were correctly classified as normal are 343 such cases and the number of normal CXR images that were incorrectly classified as COVID-19 (false positives) are 28.

4.1.4 Performance metrics of Batch 128

Table 4.1-5: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment one with batch size 128

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.745
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.062
Precision	0.902
Specificity	0.938
Accuracy	0.854
F1-Score	0.816

4.1.4.1 Visualization of Batch 128

Figure 4-8: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-9 : Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-1 batch 128

In this specific scenario, the positive class represents COVID-19 cases (labeled as 0), while the negative class represents normal CXR images (labeled as 1). The confusion matrix reveals that there are 321 true positive (TP) predictions, meaning the model correctly identified 321 COVID-19 cases. Additionally, there are 342 true negative (TN) predictions, indicating that the model correctly identified 342 normal CXR images. On the other hand, there are 54 false negatives (FN), signifying instances where the model incorrectly classified COVID-19 cases as normal, and 33 false positives (FP), indicating cases where the model incorrectly classified normal images as COVID-19.

4.1.5 Visualization of experiment-1 performance metrics

Figure 4-10: overall performance visualization of experiment-1 (data size: 5000)

Batch size 32 have given better results compared to other batch sizes. Smaller batch size like 16 lead to noisy gradients due to the smaller sample size per update, hindering

the model’s ability to generalize. Conversely, very large batch size like 128 made the model generalize poorly due to over fitting. Batch size 32 strike a balance between these extremes, allowing for more stable updates while avoiding overfitting.

4.2 Evaluation of experiment-2

Table 4.2-1: Data segmentation for experiment-2

Train Normal Image	2800	Train COVID Image	2800
Test Normal Image	600	Test COVID Image	600
Val Normal Image	600	Val COVID Image	600

In this section, total image **8000** is used. Split ratio of 70:15:15 is shown in the Table 4.2-1. Experiments is performed with different batch size with fixed epoch 15. Image are distributed with balanced condition. Each classes consist 4200 CXR data as shown in figure 4-11.

Figure 4-11: Data distribution for experiment-2

4.2.1 Performance metrics of Batch 16

Table 4.2-2: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-2 with batch size 16

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.783
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.071
Precision	0.899
Specificity	0.929

Accuracy	0.863
F1-Score	0.837

4.2.1.1 Visualization of Batch 16

Figure 4-12 : Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-13: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-2 batch 16

The matrix includes four key metrics: True Positives (TP) which is 521, indicating the number of correctly identified COVID-19 cases; False Negatives (FN) at 79, representing the instances where the model incorrectly classified COVID-19 cases as normal; False Positives (FP) at 38, signifying the cases where normal images were misclassified as COVID-19; and True Negatives (TN) at 562, representing the correct identification of normal cases.

4.2.2 Performance metrics of Batch 32

Table 4.2-3 : Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-2 with batch size 32

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.885
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.022
Precision	0.971
Specificity	0.978
Accuracy	0.937
F1-Score	0.926

4.2.2.1 Visualization of Batch 32

Figure 4-14 : Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-15: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-2 batch 32

True Positives (TP) represent the number of COVID-19 images correctly classified as positive (531), while False Negatives (FN) indicate the COVID-19 images mistakenly classified as negative (69). False Positives (FP) denote the normal images incorrectly classified as COVID-19 positive (19), and True Negatives (TN) are 581.

4.2.3 Performance metrics of Batch 64

Table 4.2-4: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-2 with batch size 64

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.949
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.056
Precision	0.933
Specificity	0.944
Accuracy	0.946
F1-Score	0.940

Sensitivity is often crucial in medical classification tasks like diagnosing COVID cases from chest X-ray images. In this case, the sensitivity is 0.949, which means that model correctly identified 94.9% of the actual COVID-positive cases in the dataset. In other words, when there was a COVID-positive case, the model detected it correctly 94.9% of the time. Precision measures how many of the predicted COVID cases were correct. With a precision of 0.933, it means that model predicted a case as COVID-positive, it was correct 93.3% of the time. In practical terms, it indicates a relatively low rate of false positives. The F1-Score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall and provides a balance between them. In this case, it's 0.940, indicating a good balance between precision and recall.

4.2.3.1 Visualization of Batch 64

Figure 4-16: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-17 : Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-2 batch 64

True Positives (TP) are 547, representing the number of COVID-19 images correctly classified as positive. False Negatives (FN) are 53, indicating the instances where COVID-19 images were incorrectly classified as negative. False Positives (FP) stand at 23, signifying normal images mistakenly classified as COVID-19 positive. Lastly, True Negatives (TN) are 577, denoting the correct identification of normal images as negative. This matrix is essential for assessing the model's accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and overall performance in distinguishing between COVID-19 and normal CXR images. The ROC curve is a graphical representation of a model's performance across different thresholds for classifying positive and negative cases. An AUC of 0.95 suggests that the model's ability to discriminate between COVID and non-COVID cases is good. The curve is close to the top-left corner, indicating a high true positive rate (sensitivity) and a low false positive rate (1 - specificity). This is indicative of a well-performing model with a strong ability to differentiate between the two classes.

4.2.4 Performance metrics of Batch 128

Table 4.2-5: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-2 with batch size 128

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.876
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.034
Precision	0.955
Specificity	0.966
Accuracy	0.926
F1-Score	0.913

4.2.4.1 Visualization of Batch 128

Figure 4-18: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-19: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-2 batch 128

The confusion matrix for classifying COVID-19 CXR (chest X-ray) images, where COVID data is labeled as 0 (positive class) and Normal Images are labeled as 1 (negative class), consists of four key metrics. True Positives (TP) which are 535, representing the number of COVID-19 images correctly classified as positive, False Negatives (FN) which are 65, indicating the instances where COVID-19 images were incorrectly classified as negative, False Positives (FP) which are 22, representing normal CXR images incorrectly classified as COVID-19 positive, and True Negatives (TN) which are 578, denoting the number of normal images correctly classified as negative for COVID-19. This matrix provides a comprehensive summary of the model's performance in terms of correctly and incorrectly classifying COVID-19 and Normal CXR images, which is essential for assessing the effectiveness of the classification model.

4.2.5 Visualization of experiment-2 performance metrics

Figure 4-20: overall performance visualization of experiment-2 (data size: 8000)

Batch size 64 shows balanced performance across most metrics, which is different to what we observed in Experiment 1. It demonstrates a good balance between sensitivity, precision, specificity, and accuracy. Batch sizes 16, 32 and 128 exhibit slightly different trends in performance, with varying degrees of sensitivity, precision, and specificity. The batch size and data size influence the optimization process, computational efficiency and generalization ability to overfitting or underfitting of machine learning models. Finding the optimal balance between these factors is essential for achieving good performance in tasks like COVID-19 classification using CNNs.

4.3 Evaluation of experiment-3

Table 4.3-1: Data segmentation for experiment-3

Train Normal Image	4550	Train COVID Image	4550
Test Normal Image	975	Test COVID Image	975
Val Normal Image	975	Val COVID Image	975

In this section, total image **13000** is used. Split ratio of 70:15:15 is shown in the Table 4.3-1. Experiments is performed with different batch size with fixed epoch 15. Image are distributed with balanced condition. Each classes consist 6500 CXR data as shown in figure 4-21.

Figure 4-21: Data distribution for experiment-3

4.3.1 Performance metrics of Batch 16

Table 4.3-2: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-3 with batch size 16

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.966
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.06
Precision	0.994
Specificity	0.994
Accuracy	0.980
F1-Score	0.979

4.3.1.1 Visualization of Batch 16

Figure 4-22: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-23: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-3 batch 16

True Positives (TP) representing the number of COVID-19 images correctly classified as positive (0), which in this case is 937; False Negatives (FN) indicating the COVID-19 images that were incorrectly classified as negative (1), with a count of 38; False Positives (FP) denoting the normal images incorrectly classified as COVID-19 positive, standing at 10; and True Negatives (TN) representing the correctly identified normal images as negative, which totals 965.

4.3.2 Performance metrics of Batch 32

Table 4.3-3: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-3 with batch size 32

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.962
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.013
Precision	0.987
Specificity	0.987
Accuracy	0.975
F1-Score	0.974

4.3.2.1 Visualization of Batch 32

Figure 4-24: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-25: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-3 batch 32

True Positives (TP) are 947, representing the number of COVID-19 CXR images correctly classified as positive. False Negatives (FN) stand at 28, indicating instances where COVID-19 images were incorrectly classified as negative. False Positives (FP) total 20, signifying the number of normal images misclassified as positive. Lastly, True Negatives (TN) are 955, indicating the correct classification of normal images as negative.

4.3.3 Performance metrics of Batch 64

Table 4.3-4: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-3 with batch size 64

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.972
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.017
Precision	0.983
Specificity	0.983
Accuracy	0.978
F1-Score	0.977

In this case, the sensitivity is 0.972, indicating that the model correctly detects approximately 97.2% of all COVID cases. A high sensitivity is crucial in a medical context to minimize false negatives, ensuring that as few COVID cases as possible are missed.

A precision of 0.983 implies that approximately 98.3% of the cases predicted as COVID-positive are correct. High precision is essential to minimize the number of false positives, which is especially important in a medical context to avoid unnecessary interventions or treatments.

4.3.3.1 Visualization of Batch 64

Figure 4-26: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-27: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-3 batch 64

The confusion matrix for classifying COVID-19 CXR (chest X-ray) images consists of four key metrics: True Positives (TP), False Negatives (FN), False Positives (FP), and

True Negatives (TN). In this specific context, where COVID data is labeled as 0 (positive class) and Normal Images are labeled as 1 (negative class), we have 951 True Positives, meaning 951 COVID-19 images were correctly identified as positive cases. There are 24 False Negatives, indicating 35 COVID-19 cases were mistakenly classified as negative. Additionally, there are 30 False Positives, where 30 normal chest X-ray images were incorrectly classified as COVID-19 positive. Finally, there are 945 True Negatives, signifying that 1229 normal images were correctly identified as negative for COVID-19. An area under the ROC curve (AUC) of 0.97 is quite high and indicates excellent discrimination ability. It shows that the model can effectively distinguish between positive and negative cases. A higher AUC generally implies better model performance.

4.3.4 Performance metrics of Batch 128

Table 4.3-5: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-3 with batch size 128

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.956
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.010
Precision	0.990
Specificity	0.990
Accuracy	0.973
F1-Score	0.972

4.3.4.1 Visualization of Batch 128

Figure 4-28: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-29: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-3 batch 128

The confusion matrix for classifying COVID-19 CXR (chest X-ray) images, with COVID data labeled as 0 (positive class) and Normal images labeled as 1 (negative class), is a table used to evaluate the performance of a classification model. In this context, there are 946 true positive cases (TP), which represents the number of COVID-19 images correctly classified as positive. There are 31 false negative cases (FN), indicating the COVID-19 images incorrectly classified as negative. There are 22 false positive cases (FP), where normal images were wrongly classified as COVID-19 positive. Finally, there are 953 true negative cases (TN), signifying the correct classification of normal images as negative. The confusion matrix provides essential metrics for assessing the accuracy and effectiveness of a COVID-19 CXR image classification model, particularly in terms of sensitivity (recall) and specificity.

4.3.5 Visualization of experiment-3 performance metrics

Figure 4-30: overall performance visualization of experiment-3 (data size: 13000)

Smaller batch sizes (16 and 32) generally result in higher sensitivity and precision, indicating better performance in correctly identifying positive cases (COVID-19) and

minimizing false positives. However, there is a trade-off with specificity, where larger batch sizes tend to perform slightly better. Larger batch sizes (64 and 128) exhibit slightly lower sensitivity and precision but higher specificity. This suggests a lower rate of false positives but potentially at the expense of missing some true positive cases. With the increase in data size from 8000 to 13000, we observe improvements in most evaluation metrics across all batch sizes. However Batch size 64 demonstrate a good balance between sensitivity, precision, and specificity, consistent with previous experiments.

4.4 Evaluation of experiment-4

Table 4.4-1: Data segmentation for experiment-4

Train Normal Image	5250	Train COVID Image	5250
Test Normal Image	1125	Test COVID Image	1125
Val Normal Image	1125	Val COVID Image	1125

In this section, total image **15000** is used. Split ratio of 70:15:15 is shown in the Table 4.4-1. Experiments is performed with different batch size with fixed epoch 15. Image are distributed with balanced condition. Each classes consist 7500 CXR data as shown in figure 4-31.

Figure 4-31: Data distribution for experiment-4

4.4.1 Performance metrics of Batch 16

Table 4.4-2: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-4 with batch size 16

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.954
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.008
Precision	0.990
Specificity	0.992
Accuracy	0.975
F1-Score	0.971

4.4.1.1 Visualization of Batch 16

Figure 4-32: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-33: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-4 batch 16

There are 1083 True Positives (TP), which represents the number of COVID-19 cases correctly identified as positive. Additionally, there are 1102 True Negatives (TN),

which indicates the number of Normal images correctly classified as negative. On the other hand, there are 42 False Negatives (FN), signifying COVID-19 cases incorrectly classified as negative, and 23 False Positives (FP), representing Normal images incorrectly identified as positive.

4.4.2 Performance metrics of Batch 32

Table 4.4-3: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-4 with batch size 32

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.968
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.008
Precision	0.980
Specificity	0.992
Accuracy	0.981
F1-Score	0.978

4.4.2.1 Visualization of Batch 32

Figure 4-34: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-35: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-4 batch 32

In this matrix, COVID-positive cases are designated as the positive class (labeled as 0), while normal images represent the negative class (labeled as 1). Among the predictions made by the model, there were 1096 true positives (TP), indicating that 1096 COVID-positive cases were correctly identified. Additionally, there were 29 false negatives (FN), meaning that 29 COVID-positive cases were incorrectly classified as negative. There were 15 false positives (FP), indicating that 15 normal images were incorrectly classified as COVID-positive. Finally, there were 1110 true negatives (TN), signifying that 1110 normal images were correctly identified as negative. This confusion matrix provides a comprehensive overview of the model's performance in distinguishing COVID-19 cases from normal cases based on CXR images.

4.4.3 Performance metrics of Batch 64

Table 4.4-4: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-4 with batch size 64

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.978
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.008
Precision	0.989
Specificity	0.991
Accuracy	0.985
F1-Score	0.983

Sensitivity, also known as Recall or Detection Rate, measures the model's ability to correctly identify all positive instances (in this case, COVID cases) among all actual

positive cases. The sensitivity is 0.978, which is quite high. It means that out of all actual COVID cases, the model correctly identifies approximately 97.8% of them.

Precision measures how many of the predicted positive instances are actually true positives. It assesses the model's accuracy when it predicts a positive class. The precision is 0.989, which is also very high. This indicates that when your model predicts a case as COVID-positive, it is correct approximately 98.9% of the time.

4.4.3.1 Visualization of Batch 64

Figure 4-36: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-37: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-4 batch 64

An area under the ROC curve (AUC) of 0.98 indicates that the model has a very high ability to distinguish between positive and negative cases. There are 1101 true positive (TP) cases, indicating that 1101 COVID-19 images were correctly classified as positive.

There are 24 false negatives (FN), which means 24 COVID-19 images were incorrectly classified as negative. Additionally, there are 13 false positives (FP), signifying that 13 normal images were incorrectly classified as COVID-19 positive. Lastly, there are 1112 true negatives (TN), showing that 1112 normal images were accurately classified as negative.

4.4.4 Performance metrics of Batch 128

Table 4.4-5: Performance evaluation metrics table for experiment-4 with batch size 128

Evaluation Metric	Value
Sensitivity or Recall or DR	0.957
False Alarm Rate (FAR)	0.013
Precision	0.984
Specificity	0.987
Accuracy	0.973
F1-Score	0.970

4.4.4.1 Visualization of Batch 128

Figure 4-38: Model Loss and Model Accuracy

Figure 4-39: Confusion Matrix and ROC curve of experiment-4 batch 128

True Positives (TP), which represent the number of correctly identified COVID-19 cases (1098); False Negatives (FN), indicating the instances where COVID-19 was present but not detected (27); False Positives (FP), denoting the cases where the model incorrectly predicted COVID-19 when it was not present (19); and True Negatives (TN), signifying the accurate identification of normal CXR images without COVID-19 (1106).

4.4.5 Visualization of experiment-4 performance metrics

Figure 4-40: overall performance visualization of experiment-4

With the increase in data size from 13000 to 15000, we observe further improvements in most evaluation metrics across all batch sizes. The larger dataset size continues to provide the model with more diverse examples to learn from, leading to better generalization and improved performance. Batch size 64 continues to demonstrate a good balance between sensitivity, precision, and specificity, consistent with previous experiments. The choice of batch size also plays a significant role, with smaller batch sizes providing better sensitivity and precision but potentially at the expense of specificity, and larger batch sizes offering higher specificity but lower sensitivity and precision. Experiment 4 reinforces the importance of both batch size and dataset size in achieving high performance in COVID-19 classification.

4.5 Analysis of batch size and data size

All these four experiment demonstrates the importance of both batch size and dataset size in achieving high performance in COVID-19 classification. Adjusting these

parameters can significantly impact the model's ability to generalize and accurately classify COVID-19 cases.

Figure 4-41: Optimal batch size respective to different data size

Among four different experiment with varying data size three experiment showed the best result with batch size 64 as shown in fig 4-41. The selection of the optimal batch size is done with the parameter metric such as recall, false alarm rate, precision and accuracy. This evaluation metric values are shown in fig 4-42.

Figure 4-42: Optimal batch size with associated experiment data size performance metric visualization

Experiment 4 have, slightly higher recall, and precision thus considered the better choice. However, the differences between the two experiments (3 and 4) with batch size 64 and data size 13000 and 15000 respectively are relatively small, and both seem to perform exceptionally well. The relationship between batch size and data size seems

crucial because it affects how the model learns from the data. However, using a larger batch size with a large data size lead to suboptimal generalization, as the model may struggle to effectively learn from the entire dataset in each iteration. Conversely, with a smaller data size, using a smaller batch size lead to overfitting, as the model may memorize the training examples instead of learning generalizable patterns. Finding right balance between batch size and data size is essential for optimizing model performance.

4.6 Learning rate fine tuning of VGG16 pipeline with optimal batch size and data size

The interplay between batch size and learning rate is crucial. Fine-tuning the learning rate of the Adam optimizer could potentially help improve the performance of model. Experiment with different magnitudes of learning rates, such as orders of magnitude ranging from (0.01, 0.001, 0.0001, 0.00001), to explore a wide range of possibilities.

Table 4.6-1: Learning rate fine tuning (Batch size: 64 and Data size: 15000)

CNN Model	Learning Rate	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	FAR
VGG16 Optimizer-Adam	0.01	93	99.2	95.1	0.5
	0.001	98.5	98.9	97.8	0.8
	0.0001	96.3	96.7	95.3	2.7
	0.00001	96.2	96.6	95.3	2.8

Using a smaller batch size often requires a smaller learning rate to avoid large updates and potential instability. However learning rate (0.001) is well-tuned for a batch size of 64. Lower learning rates lead to more stable convergence during training. This allowed the optimization algorithm to navigate more cautiously, potentially avoiding overshooting the minimum of the loss function.

4.7 Dropout regularization with optimal batch size, data size and learning rate

To prevent the model from fitting to the noise in the training data and model to learn with salient features regularization is performed with different dropout. Dropout ranging from (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5), to explore a wide range of possibilities.

Table 4.7-1: Dropout regularization for (Batch size: 64, data size: 15000 and Learning rate: 0.001)

CNN Model	Dropout	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	FAR
VGG16	0.1	80.4	83.8	75.4	0.75
	0.2	83.5	84.9	81.4	0.14
	0.3	89.5	86.9	85.4	0.11
	0.4	83.3	82.2	80.6	0.13
	0.5	83.2	81.3	79.9	0.12

The optimal dropout rate appears to be around 0.3, as it achieves the highest accuracy, precision, and recall while also reducing false alarms. However, excessively high dropout rates (e.g., 0.5) may lead to a slight decrease in performance metrics, indicating that too much regularization can harm model performance.

Figure 4-43 : Weight difference plot with dropout: 0.1

Figure 4-44: Weight difference plot with dropout: 0.2

Figure 4-45: Weight difference plot with dropout: 0.3

Figure 4-46: Weight difference plot with dropout: 0.4

Figure 4-47: Weight difference plot with dropout: 0.5

Analysis of effect of dropout on weights shows convergence behavior of model. Symmetry around zero indicates that the weights have changed equally in both positive

and negative directions thus preventing from overfitting and promoting generalization. So, looking at diagram dropout 0.2 and 0.3 provides better result.

Indeed, no statistical significance found with comparison to the table 4.6-1 after dropout regularization. VGG16 is a relatively deep convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture that already includes inherent regularization mechanisms, such as weight decay. The model already have been trained with carefully selected hyperparameters, including learning rate and batch size may be the reason dropout regularization did not provided significant improvements. Overall, the effectiveness of dropout regularization can vary depending on several factors, including the model architecture, dataset characteristics.

4.8 Comparison and analysis with other state-of-the-art model for balanced data size

Table 4.8-1: Summary of research for balanced dataset

Dataset	Base Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	FAR (%)
Datasize-1 (11000) Batch- 64	VGG16	91.2	89.4	81.2	2.1
	RESNET50V2	88.5	86.8	86.3	2.4
	INCEPTIOV3	89.3	86.3	84.8	4.9
Datasize-2 (13000) Batch- 64	VGG16	97.8	98.3	97.2	1.9
	RESNET50V2	97.5	95.8	99.3	1.7
	INCEPTIOV3	97.3	96.3	96.8	4.6
Datasize-3 (15000) Batch-64	VGG16	98.5	98.9	97.8	0.9
	RESNET50V2	99.5	98.3	99.6	0.9
	INCEPTIOV3	97.4	96.3	98.5	2.4

This experiment highlights the complex link between hyperparameter such as data size, batch size and in addition to that architectural choice of transfer learning CNN models. The table shows the results of a comparative analysis of three different state-of-the-art models for classifying chest X-rays (CXRs) of COVID-19 patients. The models were trained on three different datasets of varying sizes: Datasize-1 (11,000 images), Datasize-2 (13,000 images), and Datasize-3 (15,000 images). Each model was also trained with batch sizes: 64 and learning rate 0.001.

RESNET50V2 emerges as the optimal model for Datasize-3, offering the highest accuracy, precision, and recall while maintaining a low false alarm rate. VGG16 demonstrates strong performance, particularly for Datasize-2, making it a suitable choice for datasets of moderate size. INCEPTIONV3, while competitive, may require further optimization or tuning to match the performance of RESNET50V2 and VGG16. In larger datasets, the underlying data distribution, ResNet50V2's deeper architecture allows it to model this complexity more effectively compared to shallower architectures like VGG16 and InceptionV3, resulting in improved performance [20].

4.9 Comparison and analysis with other state-of-the-art model for imbalanced data size

Figure 4-48: Data distribution with attack ratio of 10:1

Figure 4-49: Each class of 11000 into 70:15:15 ratio Figure 4-50: Each class of 13000 into 70:15:15 ratio

Figure 4-51: Each class of 15000 into 70:15:15 ratio

Table 4.9-1: Summary of research for imbalanced data size with data ratio 70:15:15 and attack ratio of 10:1 with COVID CXR image as minority class

Dataset	Base Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	FAR
		(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Datasize-1 (11000) Batch- 64	VGG16	90.1	71.4	52.1	1.7
	RESNET50V2	81.5	56.8	48.3	1.2
	INCEPTIOV3	80.3	54.3	43.8	2.9
Datasize-2 (13000)	VGG16	93.8	76.3	61.2	1.2
	RESNET50V2	89.2	63.7	50.6	1.1

Batch- 64	INCEPTIOV3	88.3	53.2	48.4	1.8
Datasize-3 (15000)	VGG16	95.8	88.3	68.3	0.8
	RESNET50V2	91.5	62.3	52.6	1.3
Batch-64	INCEPTIOV3	92.4	57.3	59.5	1.3

Incorporating a 10:1 attack ratio with COVID CXR image as minority class in the model architecture is significant as it enables the model to effectively learn from imbalanced data distributions, improve sensitivity towards minority classes, and enhance generalization performance in real-world scenarios. For larger dataset sizes Datasize-3, where ResNet50V2 previously outperformed VGG16 in experiments with balanced data distributions, VGG16 emerges as the optimal model in the imbalanced scenario.

VGG16 Performs well overall, with the highest accuracy of 95.8% on Datasize-3 with a batch size of 64. However, its performance drops for smaller datasets and batch sizes. ResNet50V2 Shows consistent performance across datasets and batch sizes, with accuracy ranging from 89.2% to 93.8%. InceptionV3 Performs less well than the other two models. The imbalanced dataset distribution, particularly with a significant attack ratio favoring the minority class, appears to have benefited VGG16's performance. This highlights the importance of considering the impact of class imbalance on model performance and selecting appropriate model architectures.

This study emphasizes the importance of tuning hyperparameters combined with regularization techniques to enhance model generalization to unseen data. This aligns with the findings of Maram Mahmoud A. Monshi et al. [6], who suggested that tuning hyperparameters leads to better generalization. Both studies recognize the significance of regularization techniques in improving model performance. The study by K. Das et al. [8] found VGG-16 to be the best-suited model for COVID-19 detection from CXR images, which aligns with the performance observed in this research where VGG16 consistently outperformed other models in most experiments.

CHAPTER 5

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

5.1 Conclusion

The proposed tuning technique on COVID-19 and the normal CXR image classification task with the VGG16 model have achieved the optimal result while experimenting with a balanced data distribution, one with a total image of 15000 with a batch size of 64 and a learning rate of 0.001, that results in a 0.978 recall and precision of 0.989 with an accuracy of 0.985. Also, a lower FAR (0.008) indicates that it has fewer false positives, which is a desirable quality in medical diagnosis. Considering the above factors, this setting of the experiment is the better choice. In addition to this, variations in dropout showed no statistically significant effect on model performance. In the same setting, in comparison with other state-of-the-art CNN models, RESNET50V2 outperformed VGG16 with a recall of 0.996 and an accuracy of 0.995 due to its architectural depth. But while experimenting with an imbalanced data distribution for the above-optimal hyperparameter, the outcome shows VGG16 outperformed RESNET50V2, and as presented in the experiments, classifying COVID-19 CXR images proved feasible even with imbalanced data and adversarial attacks. Thus, this study demonstrated that optimizing CNN hyperparameters results in outstanding effects on the automatic extraction of features from CXR related to the classification of COVID-19.

5.2 Future Work

Additional fine-tuning of hyperparameter, such as filter size, number of epochs and loss function can be done to get precise observation and generalize model better along with data augmentation techniques. This could involve generating synthetic samples representing the underrepresented classes and investigate alternative model architectures specifically designed for handling imbalanced data and robust to adversarial attacks. This may entail ensemble techniques or designs with attention mechanisms.

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